

Dealing with personal data in research

Recommendations for research projects at the University of Basel and affiliated institutions

Authors of the checklist: Amanda Aerni, Anthea Alberto, Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Markus Bossert, Philippe Chresta, Sofia Georgakopoulou, Robert Ivanek, Lisa Ketges, Iris Lindenmann, Loredana Martignetti, Sarah Musy, Thierry Sengstag, Constantin Sluka, Isabelle Wienand.

We also thank the many people from the RDM network and the researchers who gave us feedback on the checklist.

Version 1.0, 2024-01-30

- 1) Introduction
- 2) Planning, funding and begin of a research project
 - a) Preparations
 - b) Review of your project by the Data Protection Officer or an Ethics Committee
 - c) Consent of the research participants
 - d) Agreements and contracts
- 3) Collecting, storing and analyzing data
 - a) Data collection
 - b) Data transfer
 - c) Data storage, management and analysis
- 4) Preserving, publishing and sharing data
 - a) Archiving
 - b) Presentations and Teaching
 - c) Publish and Share
- 5) Re-using data
 - a) Re-use of datasets with personal data, discovered in a research data repository
 - b) Re-use of data from another researcher or research group within the University of Basel or from researchers /research groups from another university
 - c) Re-use of patient data routinely collected during hospitalisations and ambulant visits at the University Hospital
 - d) Re-use of data which is under the governance of the Medical Faculty

1) Introduction

With this checklist we want to enable you as researchers of various disciplines of the University of Basel and affiliated institutions to deal with personal data as part of research data management (RDM). We list the most urgent aspects for each step in your research data life cycle. We recommend going through the entire document once during the project planning phase and keeping it as a checklist to guide you through your entire project. Please use it as a reference when discussing with your PI, supervisor or service providers who offer RDM support.

Research data is all data generated or (re)used during a research process. They serve to document and validate research results. It is material that can vary greatly depending on the discipline and research area and is created through various methods such as measurements, experiments, surveys, interviews, digitisation and much more. In many disciplines researchers work with personal data.

Personal data is all information relating to an identified person or a person identifiable by means of the information (see § 3 para. 3 of the Information and Data Protection Act of the Canton of Basel-Stadt [IDG]). This includes, for example, name, date of birth, email address, telephone and mobile number, OASI number, matriculation number, bank details, IP address (with exceptions), gender, photographs and also identifying characteristics (e.g. only woman in the XY team). A distinction must be made between "normal" personal data and "sensitive" personal data (see § 3 para. 4 IDG). Processing the latter entails an increased risk of causing violation of fundamental rights of the subjects due to its significance, the way it is processed and/or because it can be used to create a profile of the person concerned. Sensitive personal data includes, for example, data on children and other vulnerable persons (e.g. ethnic minorities) or information on a person's health, religious belief or ethnic background.

Please be aware that you as a researcher are **responsible** for data protection in your research project. The checklist will point you to the support services of the university that can help you with this process.

This checklist was written by the university's **data stewards** and other members of the **Research Data Management Network**. Feedback to the checklist is very welcome. Please leave comments below the wiki page or write to researchdata@unibas.ch.

Legal regulations, requirements by funders, infrastructure and tools may change. The checklist will therefore be adapted on a regular basis. The information in the following document is not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection law, contact the university's **Data Protection Officer (DPO)**.

2) Planning, funding and begin of a research project

This section lists steps to be taken and considered during the planning phase of your project. If you need help at any moment of the process please feel free to contact the [data steward](#) of your department or the [University's Research Data Management Network](#). Evaluate at the very beginning of your research project – and before you start collecting data! – whether you work with [personal data](#) in your research project. If you are working with personal data, you may have to carry out a data protection impact assessment. Whether you are obliged to carry out such an assessment depends on various factors and must be checked on a case-by-case basis. Factors include but are not limited to the processing of sensitive personal data or a large number of data subjects. Contact the DPO early in the project phase for further support.

We recommend you to use the [ethics self-assessment tool](#) provided by the University of Basel. The tool shows you the different service units of the university that you can contact for support and that can assess and approve your research project. For research projects at the University of Basel that involve personal data, the [Information and Data Protection Act of the Canton of Basel-Stadt \[IDG\]](#) always applies.

As soon as you start with your research project it is important to work towards your data management goals, like publishing your data, making it available to others in your research team or using it for teaching. The later you start, the more cumbersome it becomes. This section therefore lists many steps that you can build upon in the later phases of the research project.

Remember that certain processes, e.g. data protection reviews, ethical assessments or setting up contracts, take time (e.g. for the Ethics Committee of the University (UEK) check the meeting schedules and deadlines for handing in applications on their [website](#); for a review by the DPO you can expect a minimum timeframe of 4-6 weeks). Therefore start as early as possible, especially if you have deadlines to meet.

You can inform yourself about the legal and ethical aspects of working with personal data that are relevant in your research project with various factsheets and an [online learning tool](#) on the subject of data protection on the website of the [University's Data Protection Officer \(DPO\)](#). The website of the [Ethics Committee of the University \(UEK\)](#) also provides you with information, guidelines and useful links.

a) Preparations

- Clarify [responsibilities](#) within your project for handling data.
- Contact your IT support to check if there are fees involved for the use of secure IT environments and add these fees to your budget (e.g. in the grant application).
- Check the guidelines of your funding organization for working with personal data. These may have specific requirements for data protection and research ethics, e.g. the funding programs of the European Union. If there are inconsistencies between guidelines that apply to your research project, you have to follow the strictest guideline.
- Find out whether your faculty, department, institute or research community has guidelines and information sheets on research with personal data that you should follow. Ask your [data steward](#), PI or supervisor if you are unsure.

b) Review of your project by the Data Protection Officer or an Ethics Committee

- If your research concerns "human diseases and the structure and function of the human body", your project underlies primarily the [Human Research Act \(HRA\)](#). In this case you are obliged to submit your project to the [Ethics Committee of Northwestern and Central Switzerland \(EKNZ\)](#).
- For other research projects that are not covered by the HRA, a review by the [Ethics Committee of the University \(UEK\)](#) and/or by the [Data Protection Officer \(DPO\)](#) is not mandatory but recommended, since you stay [responsible](#) for complying with data protection law. In these cases, not the EKNZ but the [DPO](#), the [UEK](#) or – if applicable – the [Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Psychology](#) is responsible.
- Remember that if the data collection is not limited to the Canton of Basel-Stadt and/or if your research is part of a collaborative project with institutions from other cantons or countries, the data protection laws of these cantons or countries must also be complied with and other relevant ethics committees may also have to be involved. If you are unsure contact the [DPO](#) and the [UEK](#).

c) Consent of the research participants

- If you want to process personal data, in most cases you need the consent (informed or general consent) of the research participants – before you start collecting or re-using data. Please consult the [DPO](#) or the [UEK](#) and for Clinical Research the [DKF](#) for more information if you are unsure what applies in your case. In general, a written form of informed consent is recommended. If another form of consent (e.g. orally) is more appropriate in your field of research, be sure to document the consent of the research participants in another way (e.g. audio or video recording) for reasons of traceability.
- It is important to note that the wording of the informed consent form has a major influence on what you can and cannot do with your data later on. For example, you cannot publish personal data in a repository if you have not obtained the consent of the research participants. The DPO provides a [factsheet](#) on how to set up an informed consent form.
- For research methods that involve observations of people who cannot be informed because it affects their actions, we recommend seeking advice from the [UEK](#).

d) Agreements and contracts

- According to the University's [guidelines concerning contract flow](#) all research contracts must be evaluated by the Legal Service or Unitecra, depending on the field of your project.
- There are different types of contracts depending on the content:
 - Consortium Agreements typically regulate the organization of the consortium and other responsibilities as well as rules for dispute resolution. [Swiss Personal Health Network \(SPHN\)](#) provides templates for CA. Although they are aimed at SPHN project they might be used for orientation purposes.

- When the data controller decides to subcontract certain services to a third party, then a Data Transfer and Processing Agreement (DTPA) or Commissioned Data Processing Agreement (CDPA) must be concluded. Services such as cloud hosting, IT support from an external provider, or data collection by an external market research institute etc. can be subject of such agreements.
- A Data Transfer and Use agreement (DTUA) is necessary if the data controller agrees to disclose the data to a recipient for further use. The DTUA regulates the conditions under which the use of data is permitted.
- In addition, when using third-party services (e.g. transcription software, analytics software), it must be checked whether any necessary license agreements are already in place or have yet to be concluded.
- Due to the complexity of some collaborations and the diversity of the situations in question, specific advice and an individual contract should be obtained for each case. Contact the [Legal Services](#) for general support in contract matters or the [DPO](#) in matters of data protection.

3) Collecting, storing and analyzing data

Be aware that you need to choose appropriate data security measures depending on the [type of data](#) you are handling. During your research project you might deal with non-anonymized data (e.g. raw data), pseudonymized or anonymized data. Only anonymized data can be processed without special security measures.

If feasible, anonymize your data as early as possible. Anonymized data is no longer personal data. Simply removing names or keys might not be sufficient for anonymisation, when a person could be re-identified by linking the research data to publicly available data (e.g. only woman in department XY). For state of the art anonymization and pseudonymization, seek advice from your [data steward](#).

In your daily research routine, keep in mind that you are working with personal data that must be protected. Therefore also choose secure communication channels when talking about your data (e.g. when having an online meeting with your project partners and analyzing interviews together). Here you can find information on how to use Zoom for confidential conversations: <https://zoom.unibas.ch/en/privacy/>.

a) Data collection

- Define which type of data (non-anonymized, pseudonymized or anonymized data) you collect and store. If you have various data types during your research project, store them in separate folders and meet the respective security measures (see below under "c) Data storage, management and analysis").
- Make sure that all documents you need are in place, e.g. legal agreements, ethical approval, informed or general consent.
- If possible, use equipment provided by your institution (e.g. audio recorders or video cameras for interviews) to minimize security risks. The use of private end devices carries, amongst others, the risk of data (e.g. picture or audio recordings) being accidentally or automatically uploaded to cloud services or otherwise made accessible to third parties. Check with your institute /department or [IT support](#) if they lend equipment.
- Use secure data collection tools, e.g. for surveys. In case you are unsure, contact the [DPO](#).
- Choose secure communication channels when personal data is involved (e.g. secure video conferencing platforms for conducting online interviews, see e.g. [information on end-to-end encryption in Zoom](#))

b) Data transfer

Define the type of data transfer since this has implications for the tools available and the security measures to take. Within the university you can transfer the data by using the university's servers and use access management. If the data transfer is from external data provider(s) (e.g. obtaining patient data from a hospital) or to external recipient(s) (e.g. sending interview recordings to a transcription company) we recommend the following:

- Use a university provided service whenever possible (e.g. contact [sciCORE](#), [IT-Services](#), [DKF Data Science](#), etc.)
- Agree with data provider(s) or recipient(s) on:
 - Data types to be transferred
 - Pseudonymisation or anonymisation rules
 - Storing and maintaining of mapping tables
 - Used data transfer protocol
 - Where data is stored
 - When data will be deleted
- If possible, pseudonymize or anonymize data before transferring it from external data provider(s) or to external recipients.
- Transfer data with secure tools (e.g. from the university or data provider) and:
 - encrypted, in case of non-anonymized data
 - without the pseudonymization key, in case of pseudonymised data; transfer the pseudonymization key encrypted and via another secure communication channel
- For smaller amounts of data up to 300 GB [SWITCHfilesender](#) can be recommended for data transfer. See [instructions](#) by IT Services of the university.
- Consider new project-specific participant IDs for pseudonymized data, to make the merging of data from separate projects impossible.
- Make sure that data transfers are performed by a certified user (e.g. PI, Data Manager, etc.).
- [Make sure that data transfers are properly logged](#) (e.g. date, time, parties involved in the transfer (sender - receiver), eventually also transferred package information in the form of checksum / possible metadata).

c) Data storage, management and analysis

- Clarify the storage options
 - Encryption at rest (for local storage)

- Password protection
- Two-factor authentication (2FA)
- IP restrictions
- Project isolation
- Data access and modification logging
- Frequent and encrypted backups
- Use a service provided by your institution whenever possible (e.g. contact [sciCORE](#), [IT-Services](#), [DKF Data Management](#) etc.)
- Consider the following (especially if you cannot use university provided services):
- Define access groups (e.g. roles, access rights):
 - For internal data processing (e.g. who has access to which data?)
 - For data processing by third parties (e.g. hiring students for the transcription of interviews) and evaluate if a renewal of the existing contract is needed or a new contract should be made.
 - Assign different rights (read, write, modify) to different user groups and specific data sets or types
- Use secure data management and analysis tools, in doubt contact the [DPO](#) and the [Chief Information Security Officer \(CISO\)](#). Be aware that cloud-based or web-based tools have security risks and are not appropriate for personal data unless validated and approved by your institution. (For pseudonymized data cloud based storage might be okay, if the key is kept in a secure environment.)

4) Preserving, publishing and sharing data

a) Archiving

Long-term archiving of personal data is in many cases not allowed (the data retention period depends, i.a., on what is stated in the informed consent form). The data has to be deleted as soon as the purpose of data processing is accomplished. Part of the data processing is keeping the research transparent for a defined period after the end of the project (see also requirements by funders). There might be other legal regulations for keeping the data after the end of a project. For this reason:

- Define the data retention period and the archiving procedure in agreement with:
 - legal regulations (the [HRA](#) defines concrete data retention periods as well as (subject specific data protection legislation); contact the [DPO](#) for legal advice)
 - consent limits (e.g. what you have stated in informed consent forms)
 - university regulations: The University of Basel expects a minimum of 5 years for data retention after publication of the research results ([Regulation relating to academic integrity at the University of Basel, Art. 4, 8](#)).
 - the Data Transfer Agreement
 - grant agency regulations (e.g. SNSF recommends to keep data for at least 10 years)
 - see also: [use case on storage retention](#) (German only).
- Project leads and PIs are responsible for data handling. If you are not the PI, contact the PI or your supervisor for defining the data retention period and procedure.
- Send a request for archiving together with data retention periods to the ITS/sciCORE.
- Clarify who is responsible for the data after the end of the project and clarify who will delete the data after the data retention period (if necessary).
- Make certain that the data does not leave the university or gets into the hands of unauthorized people within the university.
- After projects end, delete everything from work stations, disks etc.
- Delete or destroy physical documents (e.g. informed consent sheets) when their data retention period expires.

b) Presentations and Teaching

- Clarify which part of the data can be presented
 - Use aggregated or simulated data for presentations if possible.
- If you do present or share (parts of) personal data:
 - Check if the consent agreement from the research subjects allows it.
 - Set up an agreement with the students/participants disallowing any further use of the data.
 - Make sure that personal data will be deleted after the course/lecture.

See also: [use case on teaching and presentations](#) (German only).

c) Publish and Share

Quick reminder: personal data which is anonymized can be shared without further concerns. Personal data which is not anonymized, can only be shared and published under certain conditions.

[Funders](#) and [journals](#) expect you to share and publish your data while respecting legal and ethical requirements.

- Before sharing, check if the informed consent allows sharing. If not, get back to the participants and get their consent.
- Separate the different data types (non-anonymized, pseudonymized, anonymized data), pick the appropriate repositories for sharing your (personal) data and define access restrictions if needed.
- If you have a mixed dataset, consisting also of data by third parties, please check the conditions for re-use which you signed in the Data Transfer Agreement.
- In case you are affiliated to the Medical Faculty and want to share the project's personal data, falling under the [HRA](#) under controlled access, contact the Faculty's [Data Access Committee \(MF-DAC\)](#) and collect the required documents.
- The Data Transfer Agreement has to be signed according to the current [rules](#) of the University.

5) Re-using data

Below you will find recommendations for various forms of data re-use. The RDM network also offers information sheets on the topics of [re-use of personal data](#), [repositories](#) and [re-use of material and data for research purposes](#).

This section is relevant for you in the following cases:

a) Re-use of datasets with personal data, discovered in a research data repository

- Clarify the conditions under which you are authorized to re-use the data, including licenses.
- Usually you will have to register in the repository and hand in a data access request.
- In many cases, repositories will provide you with terms of use and a contract for the use of the data.
- Some repositories expect you to contact the Data Access Committee of the providing institution in order to gain access to the respective datasets.
- Contact the [Grants Office](#) of the University of Basel, who has the role of signing officer for the University of Basel.
- Be aware that in most cases the data has to be deleted again. Be sure that you are able to comply with all requirements even if you are leaving.

b) Re-use of data from another researcher or research group within the University of Basel or from researchers/research groups from another university

- Contact the PI of the respective research project and clarify the legal and ethical conditions of re-use.
- If the data comes from another institution, contact the respective Data Access Committee of this institution to request access to the data.
- Check in particular if an informed consent has been obtained in the previous project, if it is still valid and if it covers the re-use of the data in your project.
- Clarify the Data Transfer Agreement with the respective data provider and get it reviewed by [DPO](#), [Unitectra](#), [Legal Services](#).

c) Re-use of patient data routinely collected during hospitalisations and ambulant visits at the University Hospital

- Contact the Data Governance Board of the respective hospital.

d) Re-use of data which is under the governance of the Medical Faculty

- Contact the [MF-DAC](#) to find out which requirements you have to meet to get access to the data.